

Samba 3.X and 4.X

Samba is an open-source implementation of Microsoft's SMB (Server Message Block) protocol that's being heavily used all around the world for its filesharing capabilities. Both companies and individuals, by using Linux servers or storage tend to use Samba as a storage solution for documents and any other type of data. Reasons behind that are simple - it's free of charge, it offers excellent performance and is easy to manage, and can be used with LVM and RAID to create a complete solution with easy management and excellent resiliency. It can offer Active Directory integration, openLDAP integration or use local usernames and passwords, or a username/password scheme that's separate from the Linux system it's being run on.

After almost ten years of beta-phase, Samba 4.0 brings something completely different to the world of Linux in terms of functionalities and capabilities, and that is a complete, licensed copy of Microsoft's Active Directory scheme, which in turn means that you can deploy Active Directory Domain Controllers on Samba 4.x servers now. This can significantly impact Active Directory-based IT solutions which can now be hosted on a Linux server, for free, by using Samba 4. As a part of the package, there's a preliminary support for SMB 3.0. Samba project members are developing complete SMB 3.0 compatibility, which will also feature clustered SMB 3.0 file-server implementation. Active Directory scheme in Samba 4.0 works perfectly, so we can see no reason why SMB 3.0 wouldn't be supported, as well.

Conclusion

Current state of Linux as a storage solution offers a viable solution to many small and medium-size business users. They're bit complicated to deploy, very easy to manage (mostly no management at all), have a wide array of capabilities, while at the same time retaining high levels of compatibility with predominantly Microsoft solutions that are leading the market. If Linux world can give us a standardized deduplication-capable filesystem with high resiliency natively supported by big players (like RedHat), then out-of-the-box Linux solutions can be an excellent solution for the market.

References

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- [2] RedHat Team: RedHat Enterprise Linux 6 Logical Volume Manager Administration (RedHat, 2013.)
- [3] Samba project: Samba 4.0 release notes, 2012.